

Neutrino mass models

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Prospects in neutrino physics

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Open questions

What is the origin of neutrinos masses?

Are they Dirac or Majorana?

What is the absolute scale of neutrino masses?

What is the mass ordering?

Are there more than three neutrinos? Maybe sterile?

Is there CP violation in the lepton sector?

Is lepton flavor universality violated?

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Neutrino mass models

What is the origin of neutrino masses?

Dirac vs Majorana

Paul Dirac

$$m_D \bar{f}_L f_R + \text{h.c.} = m_D \bar{f} f$$

$$f \neq f^c$$

Note:
 $f^c \equiv C \bar{f}^T$

Ettore Majorana

$$\frac{1}{2} m_M \bar{f}_X^c f_X + \text{h.c.}$$

$$f = f^c$$

Only neutral fermions can be Majorana

Experimental test

Crucial experimental test: **neutrinoless double beta decay ($0\nu\beta\beta$)**

$$2\nu\beta\beta : (A, Z) \rightarrow (A, Z + 2) + 2e^- + 2\bar{\nu}_e$$

$$0\nu\beta\beta : (A, Z) \rightarrow (A, Z + 2) + 2e^-$$

← Never observed

Many experiments:

EXO
GERDA
KamLAND-Zen
NEXT
...

Next talk by
Claudia Nones

Observation of $0\nu\beta\beta \Rightarrow$ Neutrinos are Majorana

“Black box theorem”
[Schechter, Valle, 1982]

Neutrino mass models

Neutrinos have
tiny masses

The SM must be **extended** to
account for them

(and we should try to understand
why they are small!)

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There are **MANY neutrino mass models...**

Tree-level

Radiative: 1-loop, 2-loop, 3-loop, ...

High scale

Low scale

Dimension-5: Weinberg operator

Higher dimensions: dim-7, dim-9, ...

The world of beers

↳ mass models

Round 1
Paul Dirac

Dirac neutrino masses

I am in the UK, so let me say
something about this...

Simplest neutrino mass model

How can we add **neutrino masses to the SM?**

Simplest way: just replicate what we do with the other fermions.

(1) Add **right-handed neutrinos**:

	$SU(3)_c$	$SU(2)_L$	$U(1)_Y$
ν_R	1	1	0

(2) Write **Yukawa couplings**:

$$\mathcal{L}_Y^\nu = Y_\nu \bar{\ell}_L \tilde{\Phi} \nu_R + \text{h.c.}$$

(3) Generate neutrino masses **through the Higgs VEV**:

$$\mathcal{L}_m^\nu = \mathcal{M}_\nu \bar{\nu}_L \nu_R + \text{h.c.}$$

However...

Simplest neutrino mass model

However...

$$\mathcal{M}_\nu = \frac{v}{\sqrt{2}} Y_\nu \quad \Rightarrow \quad Y_\nu \lesssim 10^{-12} \quad \text{for} \quad \mathcal{M}_\nu \lesssim 0.1 \text{ eV}$$

Just a consequence of the smallness of neutrino masses

Issues:

- **Tiny Yukawa** couplings
- **Not testable**

with such tiny Yukawa couplings no effects are foreseen

- Why not **Majorana masses** for the right-handed neutrinos?

$$\mathcal{L}_M^\nu = \frac{1}{2} \overline{\nu_R^c} M_R \nu_R + \text{h.c.}$$

A natural Dirac model

Details and other examples in [Centelles Chuliá, Srivastava, AV, 2021]

	$SU(3)_c$	$SU(2)_L$	$U(1)_Y$	$U(1)_L$	\mathbb{Z}_2
ν_R	1	1	0	1	+
$N_{L,R}$	1	1	0	1	-
<hr style="border-top: 1px dashed black;"/>					
S	1	1	0	0	-

$$\mathcal{L}^\nu = y_N \bar{\ell}_L \tilde{\Phi} N_R + y_R \bar{N}_L \nu_R S + M_N \bar{N}_L N_R + \text{h.c.}$$

Dirac mass matrix

$$\left(\bar{\nu}_L \quad \bar{N}_L \right) \begin{pmatrix} 0 & m_L \\ m_R & M_N \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \nu_R \\ N_R \end{pmatrix} + \text{h.c.}$$

$$m_L = y_N \langle \Phi \rangle$$

$$m_R = y_R \langle S \rangle$$

if $m_L \ll m_R \ll M_N$

$$m_\nu \sim m_L \frac{m_R}{M_N}$$

Dirac seesaw mechanism

Round 2
Ettore Majorana

Majorana neutrino masses

Chuck Norris fact of the day

*Chuck Norris lost his virginity
before his dad*

Majorana neutrino masses

Favorite option for most theorists (by far)

Neutrinos are “expected” to be Majorana unless some symmetry forbids lepton number violation

All simple (and theoretically appealing) models are of Majorana type. Everyone’s example: the type-I seesaw

More economical: 2 d.o.f. instead of 4

Natural in an EFT context : see [next slide](#)

In fact, Dirac neutrinos are exotic animals nowadays

However, keep in mind:
[only experiments can decide](#)

The Weinberg operator

If the New Physics states are heavy, one can describe physics at low energies by means of an **EFT**:

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{SM}}^{(4)} + \frac{1}{\Lambda} \sum_k C_k^{(5)} Q_k^{(5)} + \frac{1}{\Lambda^2} \sum_k C_k^{(6)} Q_k^{(6)} + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\Lambda^3}\right)$$

It turns out that there is only one dimension-5 operator, the so-called **Weinberg operator**:

$$Q_W = \left(\tilde{\Phi}^\dagger \ell\right)^T C \left(\tilde{\Phi}^\dagger \ell\right) \sim \ell \ell \Phi \Phi \quad [\text{Weinberg, 1979}]$$

- ⇒ Breaks **lepton number in two units** ($\Delta L = 2$)
- ⇒ Leads to **Majorana neutrino masses** after Φ gets a VEV

This has been vastly exploited by model builders

General formula

General formula for Majorana neutrino masses

$$m_\nu \propto \frac{\langle \Phi \rangle^2}{\Lambda} \times \epsilon \times \left(\frac{1}{16\pi^2} \right)^n \times \left(\frac{\langle \Phi \rangle}{\Lambda} \right)^{d-5}$$

[Bonnet et al, 2012]

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Minimal setup

Seesaw mechanism

[Bonnet et al, 2012]

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Suppression 1

Approximately conserved
lepton number

Low scale seesaw

$$\epsilon \ll 1$$

[Bonnet et al, 2012]

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Suppression 2
Loops

Radiative models

n = loop order

[Bonnet et al, 2012]

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Suppression 3

Operators with dimension
higher than 5

Dim > 5 models

d = operator dimension

[Bonnet et al, 2012]

The seesaw

Everyone's favorite model

[Minkowski, 1977]

$$\mathcal{L} = y \bar{\ell}_L \nu_R \Phi + \frac{1}{2} M_R \bar{\nu}_R^c \nu_R + \text{h.c.}$$

$$m_D = y \langle \Phi \rangle$$

ν_R : fermion singlet

$$\mathcal{M} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & m_D \\ m_D^T & M_R \end{pmatrix}$$

$$m_D \ll M_R$$

$$m_\nu = -m_D M_R^{-1} m_D^T \sim \frac{\langle \Phi \rangle^2}{M_R}$$

Natural suppression by **large scale**

Type-I seesaw

$$\nu_R \sim (1, 1, 0)$$

$$m_\nu \sim Y_\nu^2 \frac{\langle \Phi \rangle^2}{M_R}$$

Type-II seesaw

$$\Delta \sim (1, 3, 1) \sim \begin{pmatrix} \Delta^{++} \\ \Delta^+ \\ \Delta^0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$m_\nu \sim Y_\Delta \mu_\Delta \frac{\langle \Phi \rangle^2}{M_\Delta^2}$$

Type-III seesaw

$$\Sigma \sim (1, 3, 0) \sim \begin{pmatrix} \Sigma^+ \\ \Sigma^0 \\ \Sigma^- \end{pmatrix}$$

$$m_\nu \sim Y_\Sigma^2 \frac{\langle \Phi \rangle^2}{M_\Sigma}$$

Seesaw paradigm

Seesaw paradigm: Neutrino mass is generated **at a very high scale**

M_{GUT} _____

M_{SS} _____

“the
seesaw
scale”

m_{EW} _____

$\sim \langle \Phi \rangle$

$$m_\nu \propto \frac{\langle \Phi \rangle^2}{M_{SS}}$$

Naturally small if $M_{SS} \gg \langle \Phi \rangle$
(close to the GUT scale)

Seesaw paradigm

Simple & natural explanation of the smallness of neutrino masses

Connection to grand unified theories (GUTs)

$$\text{SO}(10) : \quad \mathbf{16} = \begin{pmatrix} q_L \\ u_R^c \\ d_R^c \\ \ell_L \\ e_R^c \\ \nu_R^c \end{pmatrix} \quad \mathbf{16} \cdot \mathbf{16} \cdot \mathbf{126} \quad \text{Type-I}$$

Other variants easily embedded

The seesaw arises naturally in GUTs

Impossible to test directly: the seesaw mediators are too heavy

Seesaw paradigm

Simple & natural explanation of the smallness of neutrino masses
Connection to grand unified theories (GUTs)

$16 \cdot 16 \cdot 126$ Type-I

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easily embedded

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naturally in GUTs

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The flavored majoron

Work in collaboration with **Salvador Centelles Chuliá**,
Antonio Herrero-Brocal and **Tim Herbermann**

[JHEP 01 \(2024\) 078 \[arXiv:2311.10145\]](#)

[JHEP 07 \(2024\) 060 \[arXiv:2404.15415\]](#)

[JHEP 09 \(2025\) 110 \[arXiv:2506.06449\]](#)

J

Spontaneous L violation

		$SU(3)_c$	$SU(2)_L$	$U(1)_Y$	$U(1)_L$
complex scalar	σ	1	1	0	-2

$$\mathcal{L} = y \bar{\ell}_L \nu_R \Phi + \frac{1}{2} f \sigma \bar{\nu}_R^c \nu_R + \text{h.c.}$$

$$\mathcal{V} = m_\Phi^2 \Phi^\dagger \Phi + m_\sigma^2 \sigma^* \sigma + \frac{\lambda_\Phi}{2} (\Phi^\dagger \Phi)^2 + \frac{\lambda_\sigma}{2} (\sigma^* \sigma)^2 + \lambda (\Phi^\dagger \Phi) (\sigma^* \sigma)$$

$$f \sigma \bar{\nu}_R^c \nu_R \quad \Rightarrow \quad f \langle \sigma \rangle \bar{\nu}_R^c \nu_R = M_R \bar{\nu}_R^c \nu_R$$

Any difference w.r.t. **explicit L violation**?

Spontaneous L violation

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Any difference w.r.t. **explicit L violation**?

Of course!

Spontaneous breaking of $U(1)_L$

Goldstone's theorem

A massless Goldstone boson

The **majoron**:

$$J = \text{Im}(\sigma)$$

A particularly well-motivated ALP

Explicit vs spontaneous

Claim:

Lepton number only has true meaning (= is a good quantum number for model building) if its breaking is spontaneous

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Example:

All **singlet fermion extensions** (inverse seesaw, linear seesaw, ...) with explicit lepton number violation can be seen as equivalent to a **type-I seesaw** with a specific number of singlet generations and matrix textures

$$-\mathcal{L} = y_N \bar{\ell}_L \tilde{\Phi} N + y_S \bar{\ell}_L \tilde{\Phi} S + m_R \bar{N}^c S + \frac{\mu_N}{2} \bar{N}^c N + \frac{\mu_S}{2} \bar{S}^c S + \text{h.c.}$$

$\left. \begin{array}{l} N \\ S \end{array} \right\}$ singlet fermions

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Inverse seesaw

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} N \\ S \end{array} \right\} \text{singlet fermions} \quad \mathcal{M} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & y_N \Phi & 0 \\ y_N^T \Phi & 0 & m_R \\ 0 & m_R^T & \mu_S \end{pmatrix}$$

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Linear seesaw

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} N \\ S \end{array} \right\} \text{singlet fermions} \quad \mathcal{M} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & y_N \Phi & y_S \Phi \\ y_N^T \Phi & 0 & m_R \\ y_S^T \Phi & m_R^T & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Explicit vs spontaneous

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Example:

All **singlet fermion extensions** (inverse seesaw, linear seesaw, ...) with explicit lepton number violation can be seen as equivalent to a **type-I seesaw** with a specific number of singlet generations and matrix textures

$$-\mathcal{L} = y_N \bar{\ell}_L \tilde{\Phi} N + y_S \bar{\ell}_L \tilde{\Phi} S + m_R \bar{N}^c S + \frac{\mu_N}{2} \bar{N}^c N + \frac{\mu_S}{2} \bar{S}^c S + \text{h.c.}$$

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All **singlet fermion extensions** (inverse seesaw, linear seesaw, ...) with explicit lepton number violation can be seen as equivalent to a **type-I seesaw** with a specific number of singlet generations and matrix textures

$$\begin{aligned} -\mathcal{L} &= y_N \bar{\ell}_L \tilde{\Phi} N + y_S \bar{\ell}_L \tilde{\Phi} S + m_R \bar{N}^c S + \frac{\mu_N}{2} \bar{N}^c N + \frac{\mu_S}{2} \bar{S}^c S + \text{h.c.} \\ &= Y \bar{\ell}_L \tilde{\Phi} F + \frac{M_F}{2} \bar{F}^c F + \text{h.c.} \end{aligned}$$

$\left. \begin{array}{l} N \\ S \end{array} \right\}$ **singlet fermions**

Dictionary

$$\begin{aligned} F &= \begin{pmatrix} N & S \end{pmatrix} \\ Y &= \begin{pmatrix} y_N & y_S \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad M_F = \begin{pmatrix} \mu_N & m_R \\ m_R^T & \mu_S \end{pmatrix}$$

L charges and phenomenology

This is **no longer true** if the breaking is spontaneous

(for instance, if N and S have different lepton numbers,
no dictionary can be found because they cannot be grouped together)

... and this has **physical consequences**

The choice of $U(1)_L$ charges is crucial

Two models leading to the same neutrino mass mechanism
may have **very different phenomenologies**

The **majoron** is the key

L charges and phenomenology

Inverse seesaw version 1: “canonical”

	ℓ_L	e_R	Φ	N	S	σ
$U(1)_L$	1	1	0	1	-1	-2

$$-\mathcal{L} = y_N \bar{\ell}_L \tilde{\Phi} N + m_R \bar{N}^c S + \frac{1}{2} \lambda_N \sigma \bar{N}^c N + \frac{1}{2} \lambda_S \sigma^* \bar{S}^c S + \text{h.c.}$$

$$\mathcal{M} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & y_N \Phi & 0 \\ y_N^T \Phi & \lambda_N \sigma & m_R \\ 0 & m_R^T & \lambda_S \sigma^* \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\lambda_S v_\sigma \ll y_N v \ll m_R$$

$$m_\nu \sim y_N^2 \lambda_S \frac{v^2 v_\sigma}{m_R^2}$$

Inverse seesaw version 2: “enhanced”

	ℓ_L	e_R	Φ	N	S	σ
$U(1)_L$	1	1	0	1	0	-1

$$-\mathcal{L} = y_N \bar{\ell}_L \tilde{\Phi} N + \lambda \sigma \bar{N}^c S + \frac{m_S}{2} \bar{S}^c S + \text{h.c.}$$

$$\mathcal{M} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & y_N \Phi & 0 \\ y_N^T \Phi & 0 & \lambda \sigma \\ 0 & \lambda^T \sigma & m_S \end{pmatrix}$$

$$m_S \ll y_N v \ll \lambda v_\sigma$$

$$m_\nu \sim \frac{y_N^2}{\lambda^2} \frac{v^2 m_S}{v_\sigma^2}$$

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However:
majoron coupling to
charged leptons

The majoron coupling to charged leptons

Type-I seesaw:

[Chikashige, Mohapatra, Peccei, 1981]

[Pilaftsis, 1994]

[Heeck, Patel, 2019]

$$\mathcal{L}_{J\ell\ell} = \frac{iJ}{32\pi^2 v_\sigma} \bar{\ell} \left[M_\ell \text{Tr}(yy^\dagger) \gamma_5 + 2M_\ell yy^\dagger P_L - 2yy^\dagger M_\ell P_R \right]$$

The majoron coupling to charged leptons

[Herrero-Brocal, AV, 2024]

Results applicable to generic ALPs

The majoron coupling to charged leptons

Type-I seesaw:

(+ Z diagram)

[Chikashige, Mohapatra, Peccei, 1981]

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Scotogenic model:

[Escribano, AV, 2021]

$$\mathcal{L}_{J\ell\ell} = \frac{iJ}{32\pi^2 v_S} \bar{\ell} \left(M_\ell y^\dagger \Gamma y P_L - y^\dagger \Gamma y M_\ell P_R \right) \ell$$

$$\Gamma_{mn} = \frac{M_{N_n}^2}{\left(M_{N_n}^2 - m_{\eta^+}^2 \right)^3} \left(M_{N_n}^4 - m_{\eta^+}^4 + 2 M_{N_n}^2 m_{\eta^+}^2 \log \frac{m_{\eta^+}^2}{M_{N_n}^2} \right) \delta_{mn}$$

The majoron coupling to charged leptons

Canonical inverse seesaw:

Assuming $\lambda_N = 0$
for simplicity

$$\mathcal{L}_{J\ell\ell} = -\frac{i v_\sigma J}{384\pi^2} \bar{\ell} \left[4M_\ell \text{Tr} \left(y_N \lambda_S \lambda_S^\dagger m_R^{-2} y_N^\dagger \right) \gamma_5 \right. \\ \left. + 5 M_\ell y_N \lambda_S \lambda_S^\dagger m_R^{-2} y_N^\dagger P_L - 5 y_N \lambda_S \lambda_S^\dagger m_R^{-2} y_N^\dagger M_\ell P_R \right] \ell$$

$$g_{J\ell\ell} \sim \frac{y_N^2 \lambda_S^2}{96\pi^2} \frac{M_\ell v_\sigma}{m_R^2}$$

Enhanced inverse seesaw:

$$\mathcal{L}_{J\ell\ell} = \frac{iJ}{32\pi^2 v_\sigma} \bar{\ell} \left[M_\ell \text{Tr}(y_N y_N^\dagger) \gamma_5 \right. \\ \left. + 2M_\ell y_N y_N^\dagger P_L - 2 y_N y_N^\dagger M_\ell P_R \right] \ell$$

$$g_{J\ell\ell} \sim \frac{y_N^2}{16\pi^2} \frac{M_\ell}{v_\sigma}$$

(+ Z diagrams)

L charges and phenomenology

Inverse seesaw version 1: “canonical”

	ℓ_L	e_R	Φ	N	S	σ
$U(1)_L$	1	1	0	1	-1	-2

$J = \text{Im}(\sigma)$

$$\mathcal{M} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & y_N \Phi & 0 \\ y_N^T \Phi & \lambda_N \sigma & m_R \\ 0 & m_R^T & \lambda_S \sigma^* \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\lambda_S v_\sigma \ll y_N v \ll m_R$$

$$m_\nu \sim y_N^2 \lambda_S \frac{v^2 v_\sigma}{m_R^2}$$

Inverse seesaw version 2: “enhanced”

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$$g_{J\ell\ell} \sim \frac{y_N^2 \lambda_S^2}{96\pi^2} \frac{M_\ell v_\sigma}{m_R^2} \sim \frac{\lambda_S}{96\pi^2} \frac{M_\ell m_\nu}{v^2}$$

Inverse seesaw version 2: “enhanced”

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$$\lambda_S v_\sigma \ll y_N v \ll m_R$$

$$m_\nu \sim y_N^2 \lambda_S \frac{v^2 v_\sigma}{m_R^2}$$

$$g_{J\ell\ell} \sim \frac{y_N^2 \lambda_S^2}{96\pi^2} \frac{M_\ell v_\sigma}{m_R^2} \sim \frac{\lambda_S}{96\pi^2} \frac{M_\ell m_\nu}{v^2}$$

Inverse seesaw version 2: “enhanced”

	ℓ_L	e_R	Φ	N	S	σ
$U(1)_L$	1	1	0	1	0	-1

$J = \text{Im}(\sigma)$

$$\mathcal{M} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & y_N \Phi & 0 \\ y_N^T \Phi & 0 & \lambda \sigma \\ 0 & \lambda^T \sigma & m_S \end{pmatrix}$$

$$m_S \ll y_N v \ll \lambda v_\sigma$$

$$m_\nu \sim \frac{y_N^2}{\lambda^2} \frac{v^2 m_S}{v_\sigma^2}$$

$$g_{J\ell\ell} \sim \frac{y_N^2}{16\pi^2} \frac{M_\ell}{v_\sigma}$$

Not suppressed by m_ν

Lepton flavor violation

The majoron opens up new **exotic LFV channels**

How do they compare to the *traditional ones*?

Enhanced inverse seesaw:

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \Gamma(\ell_\alpha \rightarrow \ell_\beta J) \sim \frac{m_{\ell_\alpha}^3}{v_\sigma^2} \\ \Gamma(\ell_\alpha \rightarrow \ell_\beta \gamma) \sim \frac{m_{\ell_\alpha}^5}{m_R^4} \end{array} \right\} \Rightarrow \frac{\text{BR}(\ell_\alpha \rightarrow \ell_\beta \gamma)}{\text{BR}(\ell_\alpha \rightarrow \ell_\beta J)} \sim \left(\frac{m_{\ell_\alpha}}{m_R} \right)^2 \lambda^{-2} \ll 1$$

(unless $\lambda \ll 1$)

They could easily be **dominant**

Enhanced inverse seesaw

Yellow: $Y \sim \mathcal{O}(1)$

Blue: $Y \ll \mathcal{O}(1)$

Very few points
will be probed
by MEG-II

$$\mu \rightarrow eJ$$

is much better than

$$\mu \rightarrow e\gamma$$

to test the model

Complementary probes
from cosmology

[Centelles Chuliá, Herbermann,
Herrero-Brocal, AV, 2025]

Final remarks

Take-home messages

Neutrinos push us beyond the Standard Model. In fact, the lepton sector still contains many unknowns

There are **many models**. I ended up discussing models with a majoron, but many more well-motivated scenarios exist

Neutrino model building is a very **active** field. Many relevant subjects were not covered in this talk: flavor models, modular symmetries, radiative models, ...

Take-home messages

Neutrinos push us beyond the Standard Model. In fact, the lepton sector still contains many unknowns

There are **many models**. I ended up discussing models with a majoron, but many more well-motivated scenarios exist

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Happy 2026!

Backup slides

Dirac vs Majorana

Dirac neutrinos

$$m_D \bar{f}_L f_R + \text{h.c.} = m_D \bar{f} f$$

Different antiparticle

Combination of independent L and R Weyl fermions

4 d.o.f.

Conserves U(1) charges

$$\Delta L = 0$$

Majorana neutrinos

$$\frac{1}{2} m_M \bar{f}_X^c f_X + \text{h.c.}$$

They are **their own antiparticle**

Combination of a Weyl fermion and its conjugate

2 d.o.f.

Violates all U(1) charges

$$\Delta L = 2$$

Only ν can be Majorana

Neutrino oscillations

normal hierarchy (NH)

inverted hierarchy (IH)

To be determined by the next generation of long-baseline experiments (**Dune** & **Hyper-K**)

Leptonic mixing matrix

$$V_{\text{CKM}} = U_u^\dagger U_d$$

CKM

$$V_{\text{PMNS}} = U_e^\dagger U_\nu$$

PMNS

Neutrino oscillations

parameter	best fit $\pm 1\sigma$	2σ range	3σ range
$\Delta m_{21}^2 [10^{-5} \text{eV}^2]$	$7.50^{+0.22}_{-0.20}$	7.12–7.93	6.94–8.14
$ \Delta m_{31}^2 [10^{-3} \text{eV}^2]$ (NO)	$2.55^{+0.02}_{-0.03}$	2.49–2.60	2.47–2.63
$ \Delta m_{31}^2 [10^{-3} \text{eV}^2]$ (IO)	$2.45^{+0.02}_{-0.03}$	2.39–2.50	2.37–2.53
$\sin^2 \theta_{12} / 10^{-1}$	3.18 ± 0.16	2.86–3.52	2.71–3.69
$\theta_{12} / ^\circ$	34.3 ± 1.0	32.3–36.4	31.4–37.4
$\sin^2 \theta_{23} / 10^{-1}$ (NO)	5.74 ± 0.14	5.41–5.99	4.34–6.10
$\theta_{23} / ^\circ$ (NO)	49.26 ± 0.79	47.37–50.71	41.20–51.33
$\sin^2 \theta_{23} / 10^{-1}$ (IO)	$5.78^{+0.10}_{-0.17}$	5.41–5.98	4.33–6.08
$\theta_{23} / ^\circ$ (IO)	$49.46^{+0.60}_{-0.97}$	47.35–50.67	41.16–51.25
$\sin^2 \theta_{13} / 10^{-2}$ (NO)	$2.200^{+0.069}_{-0.062}$	2.069–2.337	2.000–2.405
$\theta_{13} / ^\circ$ (NO)	$8.53^{+0.13}_{-0.12}$	8.27–8.79	8.13–8.92
$\sin^2 \theta_{13} / 10^{-2}$ (IO)	$2.225^{+0.064}_{-0.070}$	2.086–2.356	2.018–2.424
$\theta_{13} / ^\circ$ (IO)	$8.58^{+0.12}_{-0.14}$	8.30–8.83	8.17–8.96
δ / π (NO)	$1.08^{+0.13}_{-0.12}$	0.84–1.42	0.71–1.99
$\delta / ^\circ$ (NO)	194^{+24}_{-22}	152–255	128–359
δ / π (IO)	$1.58^{+0.15}_{-0.16}$	1.26–1.85	1.11–1.96
$\delta / ^\circ$ (IO)	284^{+26}_{-28}	226–332	200–353

Table from de Salas et al

Similar results by other groups

Degeneracies broken by
matter effects

Both **orderings** are possible:

Normal Hierarchy (NO)

$$m_{\nu_1} < m_{\nu_2} < m_{\nu_3}$$

Inverted Hierarchy (IO)

$$m_{\nu_3} < m_{\nu_1} < m_{\nu_2}$$

However: preference for NO

Slight preference for θ_{23} in the
second octant

SM particle masses

Particle	Log10 (m eV)
neutrino	0
electron	5,71
muon	8,02
tau	9,23
u quark	6,6
d quark	6,85
s quark	8
c quark	9,08
b quark	9,6
t quark	11,24
W boson	10,9
Z boson	10,96
Higgs	11,06

The neutrino looks special, right?

Constraints on the majoron

A massless majoron is allowed as long as its couplings to matter are suppressed

This restricts its **representation** under the gauge symmetry

A bit of **history**...

[Chikashige, Mohapatra, Peccei, 1981] **Singlet** majoron: $J = \text{Im}(\sigma)$

First appearance of the majoron

Singlet majoron model (the model we just discussed)

[Gelmini, Roncadelli, 1981] **Triplet** majoron: $J = \text{Im}(\Delta^0)$

[Aulakh, Mohapatra, 1982] **Doublet** majoron: $J = \text{Im}(\tilde{\nu}_L)$

Both **excluded** due to the unsuppressed majoron couplings to gauge bosons

[Schechter, Valle, 1982] **Singlet-Doublet-Triplet** admixture

Allowed as long as the majoron is **mostly singlet**

Constraints on the majoron

A massless majoron is allowed as long as its couplings to matter are suppressed

⇒ Singlet majoron

Stringent bounds from **astrophysics**

$$g_{Jee} < 2.1 \cdot 10^{-13}$$

$$g_{J\mu\mu} < 2.1 \cdot 10^{-10}$$

Also bounds from **LFV** searches

$$g_{Jee} < 5.7 \cdot 10^{-11}$$

[Escribano, AV, 2021]

Odds and ends

Majoron at colliders Missing energy. Potentially dangerous $h \rightarrow J J$

Majoron dark matter Needs a non-zero mass (explicit L violation)

Majoron in leptogenesis

[Aristizábal Sierra, Tórtola, Valle, AV, 2014] [Brune, 2023] [Wada, 2024]

[Chun, Jung, 2024] [King, Manna, Roshan, Sil, 2025]

Multimajoron models

[Di Bari, King, Rahat, 2024] [Fu, Ghoshal, King, 2025]

Majoron as an axion-like particle

Unobservable LFV?

SM + Dirac neutrino masses

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{cc}}^{\ell} = \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} \bar{e}_L \gamma_{\mu} V_{\text{PMNS}} \hat{\nu}_L W^{-\mu} + \text{h.c.}$$

V_{PMNS} : lepton mixing matrix

[analog of the CKM matrix in the lepton sector]

$$\text{BR}(\mu \rightarrow e \gamma) = \frac{3\alpha}{32\pi} \left| \sum_i (V_{\text{PMNS}})_{\mu i}^* (V_{\text{PMNS}})_{e i} \left(\frac{m_{\nu_i}}{m_W} \right)^2 \right|^2$$

$$\lesssim 10^{-54}$$

Since neutrino masses are the **only source** of LFV, all CLFV amplitudes are strongly suppressed (in fact, **GIM** suppressed)

A philosophical moment

Occam's razor:

The simplest explanation is the correct one

Occam's laser:

The most awesome explanation is the correct one

Occam's hammer:

My explanation is the correct one

All credit goes to
Alberto Aparici